

Lot Name	Young (up to 19)			Working-Age (20 to 69)			Senior (70 and above)			Total		
	Deaths	Doses	Mortality(%)	Deaths	Doses	Mortality(%)	Deaths	Doses	Mortality(%)	Deaths	Doses	Mortality(%)
GJ7141	6	7,762	0.08	358	95,117	0.38	3,364	99,746	3.37	3,728	202,625	1.840
FN2723	4	13,091	0.03	599	169,071	0.35	2,896	75,490	3.84	3,499	257,652	1.358
GK1328	4	4,230	0.09	243	63,477	0.38	3,244	99,828	3.25	3,491	167,535	2.084
GJ9259	3	5,268	0.06	267	72,973	0.37	2,705	98,388	2.75	2,975	176,629	1.684
FW0547	2	10,370	0.02	301	87,207	0.35	2,356	74,414	3.17	2,659	171,991	1.546
FP9654	1	7,826	0.01	205	63,939	0.32	2,440	118,955	2.05	2,646	190,720	1.387
GJ7139	1	4,836	0.02	278	68,970	0.40	2,344	79,095	2.96	2,623	152,901	1.715
FJ5929	1	4,372	0.02	166	77,215	0.21	2,442	84,760	2.88	2,609	166,347	1.568
GJ1836	4	6,332	0.06	337	88,642	0.38	2,267	81,722	2.77	2,608	176,696	1.476
FP9647	12	26,318	0.05	283	93,704	0.30	2,242	90,731	2.47	2,537	210,753	1.204
GL8592	0	2,516	0.00	184	44,032	0.42	2,213	69,614	3.18	2,397	116,162	2.063
FM7534	13	31,099	0.04	418	119,664	0.35	1,944	82,583	2.35	2,375	233,346	1.018
EY5423	0	421	0.00	76	57,304	0.13	2,236	131,644	1.70	2,312	189,369	1.221
GJ1852	3	3,373	0.09	241	57,145	0.42	2,067	78,876	2.62	2,311	139,394	1.658
GJ2674	0	3,414	0.00	196	49,155	0.40	1,986	53,431	3.72	2,182	106,000	2.058
GD9572	1	3,745	0.03	346	73,242	0.47	1,833	45,603	4.02	2,180	122,590	1.778
HG2347	0	2,593	0.00	157	41,434	0.38	2,007	34,334	5.85	2,164	78,361	2.762
EW0201	0	1,077	0.00	118	66,446	0.18	1,950	111,468	1.75	2,068	178,991	1.155
FA7338	1	1,197	0.08	110	66,599	0.17	1,940	111,783	1.74	2,051	179,579	1.142
FL7646	1	2,376	0.04	153	54,817	0.28	1,835	66,585	2.76	1,989	123,778	1.607
FM3289	0	3,830	0.00	236	61,664	0.38	1,732	62,197	2.78	1,968	127,691	1.541
GD9568	1	6,508	0.02	416	103,702	0.40	1,518	27,904	5.44	1,935	138,114	1.401
FC9880	0	4,090	0.00	308	129,655	0.24	1,616	79,585	2.03	1,924	213,330	0.902
EY3860	0	473	0.00	93	52,348	0.18	1,829	112,415	1.63	1,922	165,236	1.163
FT9319	3	8,575	0.03	233	70,861	0.33	1,668	67,605	2.47	1,904	147,041	1.295
FK0595	0	2,526	0.00	168	45,779	0.37	1,732	66,680	2.60	1,900	114,985	1.652
FC3661	0	616	0.00	90	60,509	0.15	1,761	112,344	1.57	1,851	173,469	1.067
GL1585	2	3,239	0.06	181	39,506	0.46	1,639	45,430	3.61	1,822	88,175	2.066
FA5765	1	1,228	0.08	74	62,547	0.12	1,729	113,317	1.53	1,804	177,092	1.019
FA2453	0	338	0.00	63	51,990	0.12	1,697	140,807	1.21	1,760	193,135	0.911
EW0207	0	1,315	0.00	111	68,087	0.16	1,517	66,329	2.29	1,628	135,731	1.199
GJ9258	1	2,242	0.04	153	32,810	0.47	1,434	44,052	3.26	1,588	79,104	2.007
GD9574	0	2,053	0.00	161	38,449	0.42	1,404	45,694	3.07	1,565	86,196	1.816
FC5947	0	3,407	0.00	125	74,977	0.17	1,414	63,899	2.21	1,539	142,283	1.082
EW0203	1	610	0.16	93	60,760	0.15	1,442	78,218	1.84	1,536	139,588	1.100
FR4768	4	10,745	0.04	284	88,733	0.32	1,216	33,171	3.67	1,504	132,649	1.134
FT8584	1	6,974	0.01	155	48,783	0.32	1,320	54,911	2.40	1,476	110,668	1.334
GE6396	0	1,008	0.00	109	25,111	0.43	1,354	40,073	3.38	1,463	66,192	2.210
Z10007A	0	54	0.00	37	4,148	0.89	1,423	7,974	17.85	1,460	12,176	11.991
GJ5751	0	3,021	0.00	148	36,127	0.41	1,294	28,120	4.60	1,442	67,268	2.144
FC5295	0	687	0.00	79	53,751	0.15	1,342	64,672	2.08	1,421	119,110	1.193
GD9571	1	1,032	0.10	140	32,937	0.43	1,255	37,194	3.37	1,396	71,163	1.962
HJ3098	0	1,058	0.00	100	17,616	0.57	1,280	17,967	7.12	1,380	36,641	3.766
FK7441	6	30,821	0.02	259	105,968	0.24	1,088	31,289	3.48	1,353	168,078	0.805
GJ1857	2	2,773	0.07	128	37,139	0.34	1,218	38,790	3.14	1,348	78,702	1.713
FF0843	1	7,246	0.01	273	143,988	0.19	1,069	34,617	3.09	1,343	185,851	0.723
EX3617	0	196	0.00	44	35,613	0.12	1,262	83,059	1.52	1,306	118,868	1.099
FD0889	1	2,602	0.04	134	73,226	0.18	1,120	51,133	2.19	1,255	126,961	0.988
FC8736	0	1,241	0.00	109	53,395	0.20	1,142	45,595	2.50	1,251	100,231	1.248
FK6302	7	36,294	0.02	270	113,546	0.24	961	24,601	3.91	1,238	174,441	0.710
EY0572	0	1,957	0.00	148	70,150	0.21	1,088	49,571	2.19	1,236	121,678	1.016
FR1790	1	3,488	0.03	107	33,917	0.32	1,099	48,879	2.25	1,207	86,284	1.399
FN2726	2	6,040	0.03	161	46,456	0.35	989	25,535	3.87	1,152	78,031	1.476
Z10015A	0	173	0.00	54	8,905	0.61	1,077	12,855	8.38	1,131	21,933	5.157
EY2173	0	678	0.00	52	63,849	0.08	1,069	98,766	1.08	1,121	163,293	0.686
FN9605	1	11,903	0.01	242	80,074	0.30	863	21,285	4.05	1,106	113,262	0.976
Z10011A	0	319	0.00	50	14,090	0.35	1,032	20,656	5.00	1,082	35,065	3.086
EY0779	0	343	0.00	33	23,564	0.14	1,047	70,901	1.48	1,080	94,808	1.139
GJ7142	0	152	0.00	47	14,731	0.32	1,015	22,549	4.50	1,062	37,432	2.837
000218A	0	675	0.00	93	28,484	0.33	921	24,071	3.83	1,014	53,230	1.905
FA4597	0	162	0.00	21	16,329	0.13	991	94,370	1.05	1,012	110,861	0.913
FC9909	0	729	0.00	82	61,743	0.13	930	43,677	2.13	1,012	106,149	0.953
3006279	0	616	0.00	104	30,226	0.34	858	27,313	3.14	962	58,155	1.654
Z10008A	1	195	0.51	41	6,361	0.64	859	8,073	10.64	901	14,629	6.159
FF2782	3	14,977	0.02	341	199,504	0.17	554	11,289	4.91	898	225,770	0.398
000276A	0	673	0.00	104	39,860	0.26	779	19,653	3.96	883	60,186	1.467
HD9868	0	310	0.00	50	9,304	0.54	831	14,933	5.56	881	24,547	3.589
000006A	0	179	0.00	70	20,805	0.34	789	22,848	3.45	859	43,832	1.960
000214A	0	818	0.00	156	53,570	0.29	688	34,450	2.00	844	88,838	0.950
000220A	0	280	0.00	59	22,358	0.26	782	21,469	3.64	841	44,107	1.907
FK0108	4	26,606	0.02	219	96,679	0.23	614	16,439	3.74	837	139,724	0.599
000026A	0	832	0.00	213	73,462	0.29	608	47,674	1.28	821	121,968	0.673
Z10014A	0	238	0.00	48	8,613	0.56	767	11,469	6.69	815	20,320	4.011
FK8562	6	34,525	0.02	240	103,122	0.23	540	12,362	4.37	786	150,009	0.524
EY5422	0	235	0.00	27	14,795	0.18	759	32,351	2.35	786	47,381	1.659
GK7844	0	803	0.00	64	13,995	0.46	682	20,431	3.34	746	35,229	2.118
000193A	1	1,406	0.07	98	46,015	0.21	637	36,528	1.74	736	83,949	0.877
000237A	0	482	0.00	74	22,569	0.33	661	24,527	2.69	735	47,578	1.545
FP8795	3	5,488	0.05	204	59,559	0.34	502	11,925	4.21	709	76,972	0.921
3005840	0	1,679	0.00	115	36,557	0.31	592	21,501	2.75	707	59,737	1.184
FF4204	1	7,806	0.01	195	117,231	0.17	506	20,984	2.41	702	146,021	0.481
EY5420	0	569	0.00	35	41,394	0.08	662	48,562	1.36	697	90,525	0.770
EW4811	0	556	0.00	23	68,133	0.03	665	24,450	2.72	688	93,139	0.739
000005A	0	767	0.00	139	36,304	0.38	542	13,565	4.00	681	50,636	1.345
3006343	0	220	0.00	83	26,911	0.31	596	23,290	2.56	679	50,421	1.347
000021A	0	269	0.00	73	28,936	0.25	598	29,298	2.04	671	58,503	1.147
FA5829	0	187	0.00	37	16,755	0.22	624	45,191	1.38	661	62,133	1.064
EY0583	0	2,460	0.00	122	67,946	0.18	523	17,417	3.00	645	87,823	0.734
000018A	0	357	0.00	80	21,659	0.37	549	13,934	3.94	629	35,950	1.750
000233A	0	421	0.00	50	20,135	0.25	578	23,752	2.43	628	44,308	1.417

Table S1

Lot Name	Young (up to 19)			Working-Age (20 to 69)			Senior (70 and above)			Total		
	Deaths	Doses	Mortality(%)	Deaths	Doses	Mortality(%)	Deaths	Doses	Mortality(%)	Deaths	Doses	Mortality(%)
FK9942	0	1	0.00	0	8	0.00	2	5	40.00	2	14	14.286
FL0108	0	0	0.00	0	1	0.00	2	13	15.38	2	14	14.286
FP1790	0	0	0.00	0	4	0.00	4	28	14.29	4	32	12.500
FJ7646	0	0	0.00	1	15	6.67	3	18	16.67	4	33	12.121
710007A	0	54	0.00	37	4,148	0.89	1,423	7,974	17.85	1,460	12,176	11.991
2000054A	0	0	0.00	0	0	0.00	2	18	11.11	2	18	11.111
FBB162	0	1	0.00	0	6	0.00	1	2	50.00	1	9	11.111
710010A	0	10	0.00	8	1,152	0.69	312	1,987	15.70	320	3,149	10.162
HU3098	0	1	0.00	1	15	6.67	3	24	12.50	4	40	10.000
FAB736	0	1	0.00	0	8	0.00	1	1	100.00	1	10	10.000
FT9647	0	0	0.00	0	18	0.00	2	5	40.00	2	23	8.696
710002C	0	15	0.00	5	644	0.78	115	769	14.95	120	1,428	8.403
FA5767	0	0	0.00	0	3	0.00	3	33	9.09	3	36	8.333
FP9674	0	1	0.00	0	5	0.00	1	6	16.67	1	12	8.333
FK7646	0	0	0.00	0	15	0.00	3	22	13.64	3	37	8.108
GJ8592	0	1	0.00	0	33	0.00	4	17	23.53	4	51	7.843
EW2173	0	0	0.00	0	4	0.00	4	48	8.33	4	52	7.692
400094A	0	0	0.00	0	4	0.00	4	52	7.69	4	56	7.143
FN9606	0	2	0.00	0	5	0.00	1	7	14.29	1	14	7.143
GJ1585	0	0	0.00	1	25	4.00	3	33	9.09	4	58	6.897
EY3617	0	0	0.00	0	14	0.00	2	16	12.50	2	30	6.667
FR9654	0	1	0.00	0	13	0.00	2	16	12.50	2	30	6.667
FL2723	0	0	0.00	0	17	0.00	2	14	14.29	2	31	6.452
710003A	0	56	0.00	9	1,741	0.52	225	1,850	12.16	234	3,647	6.416
810001A	0	0	0.00	0	3	0.00	2	29	6.90	2	32	6.250
EW4834	0	0	0.00	0	5	0.00	1	11	9.09	1	16	6.250
FM2723	0	2	0.00	1	10	10.00	0	4	0.00	1	16	6.250
Comirnaty	0	0	0.00	0	78	0.00	32	438	7.31	32	516	6.202
710008A	1	195	0.51	41	6,361	0.64	859	8,073	10.64	901	14,629	6.159
HG2773	0	0	0.00	0	8	0.00	1	9	11.11	1	17	5.882
300318	0	0	0.00	0	2	0.00	1	16	6.25	1	18	5.556
FP8584	0	1	0.00	0	9	0.00	1	8	12.50	1	18	5.556
710005A	0	109	0.00	16	3,078	0.52	408	4,854	8.41	424	8,041	5.273
LL7363	0	0	0.00	0	3	0.00	1	16	6.25	1	19	5.263
710015A	0	173	0.00	54	8,905	0.61	1,077	12,855	8.38	1,131	21,933	5.157
710002B	0	44	0.00	0	574	0.00	46	320	14.38	46	938	4.904
N004A	0	0	0.00	0	20	0.00	1	1	100.00	1	21	4.762
VPA003A	0	21	0.00	1	465	0.22	33	254	12.99	34	740	4.595
000305A	0	14	0.00	7	1,678	0.42	120	1,090	11.01	127	2,782	4.565
400095A	0	10	0.00	10	2,233	0.45	287	4,387	6.54	297	6,630	4.480
810001B	0	0	0.00	0	5	0.00	2	40	5.00	2	45	4.444
710004A	0	146	0.00	14	3,880	0.36	305	3,302	9.24	319	7,328	4.353
LK7365	0	0	0.00	0	39	0.00	14	283	4.95	14	322	4.348
FK8652	0	0	0.00	0	16	0.00	1	7	14.29	1	23	4.348
000318A	0	2	0.00	0	152	0.00	9	55	16.36	9	209	4.306
710014A	0	238	0.00	48	8,613	0.56	767	11,469	6.69	815	20,320	4.011
FJ7441	0	1	0.00	0	12	0.00	1	12	8.33	1	25	4.000
FM9605	0	2	0.00	0	23	0.00	1	1	100.00	1	26	3.846
HH3284	0	401	0.00	24	5,746	0.42	410	5,212	7.87	434	11,359	3.821
HJ3098	0	1,058	0.00	100	17,616	0.57	1,280	17,967	7.12	1,380	36,641	3.766
000249A	0	22	0.00	0	429	0.00	27	276	9.78	27	727	3.714
EJ5929	0	0	0.00	0	22	0.00	2	32	6.25	2	54	3.704
400190A	0	4	0.00	5	360	1.39	27	516	5.23	32	880	3.636
HD9868	0	310	0.00	50	9,304	0.54	831	14,933	5.56	881	24,547	3.589
FN8795	0	3	0.00	1	23	4.35	1	30	3.33	2	56	3.571
GK5751	0	0	0.00	0	5	0.00	1	23	4.35	1	28	3.571
HG2273	0	1,641	0.00	354	65,952	0.54	6,429	124,676	5.16	6,783	192,269	3.528
HH1299	0	2,886	0.00	274	59,689	0.46	4,153	64,761	6.41	4,427	127,336	3.477
000301A	0	33	0.00	8	2,110	0.38	104	1,099	9.46	112	3,242	3.455
HG2346	0	1,752	0.00	385	68,188	0.56	5,185	104,294	4.97	5,570	174,234	3.197
HG2251	0	998	0.00	303	56,872	0.53	5,173	113,562	4.56	5,476	171,432	3.194
HG2348	1	3,057	0.03	291	61,191	0.48	3,823	64,931	5.89	4,115	129,179	3.186
HG2352	1	2,413	0.04	399	73,888	0.54	5,140	101,365	5.07	5,540	177,666	3.118
400181A	0	19	0.00	12	3,917	0.31	393	9,120	4.31	405	13,056	3.102
710011A	0	319	0.00	50	14,090	0.35	1,032	20,656	5.00	1,082	35,065	3.086
000511A	0	26	0.00	0	88	0.00	4	16	25.00	4	130	3.077
EY2453	0	0	0.00	1	24	4.17	0	9	0.00	1	33	3.030
FW0207	0	0	0.00	0	9	0.00	1	24	4.17	1	33	3.030
HH1229	0	3	0.00	1	20	5.00	0	10	0.00	1	33	3.030
EC3861	0	2	0.00	0	63	0.00	5	102	4.90	5	167	2.994
HG5983	0	289	0.00	33	6,203	0.53	317	5,301	5.98	350	11,793	2.968
VPA017A	0	0	0.00	0	23	0.00	15	483	3.11	15	506	2.964
4000186A	0	3	0.00	0	97	0.00	8	171	4.68	8	271	2.952
400194A	0	33	0.00	25	3,428	0.73	323	8,798	3.67	348	12,259	2.839
GJ7142	0	152	0.00	47	14,731	0.32	1,015	22,549	4.50	1,062	37,432	2.837
000248A	0	49	0.00	21	5,573	0.38	306	6,037	5.07	327	11,659	2.805
HG2347	0	2,593	0.00	157	41,434	0.38	2,007	34,334	5.85	2,164	78,361	2.762
GK1329	0	575	0.00	35	8,779	0.40	449	8,361	5.37	484	17,715	2.732
000300A	0	29	0.00	13	2,731	0.48	117	2,079	5.63	130	4,839	2.687
EM0207	0	0	0.00	0	38	0.00	2	38	5.26	2	76	2.632
FY5420	0	1	0.00	1	30	3.33	0	7	0.00	1	38	2.632
VPA006A	0	20	0.00	1	245	0.41	10	159	6.29	11	424	2.594
FA3860	0	0	0.00	0	12	0.00	1	27	3.70	1	39	2.564
FP7280	0	0	0.00	0	14	0.00	2	65	3.08	2	79	2.532
HG2246	0	0	0.00	0	11	0.00	1	29	3.45	1	40	2.500
HG1299	0	1	0.00	1	54	1.85	1	26	3.85	2	81	2.469
000268A	0	52	0.00	20	2,942	0.68	119	2,714	4.38	139	5,708	2.435
FF8162	0	3	0.00	1	39	2.56	0	0	0.00	1	42	2.381
FM9654	0	0	0.00	0	12	0.00	1	30	3.33	1	42	2.381
GE0905	0	27	0.00	22	5,538	0.40	399	12,272	3.25	421	17,837	2.360

Table S2

Rank	Lot Name	Death count
1	FM3289	10
2	GJ7140	9
3	FJ5929	7
4	FN2723	6
5	HG2348	6
6	000028A	5
7	FA7338	5
8	FL7646	5
9	FP9654	5
10	GJ2674	5
11	GJ2675	5
12	HG2251	5
13	HG2346	5
14	000021A	4
15	FC3661	4
16	FL1839	4
17	GD9574	4
18	000026A	3
19	000260A	3
20	EY2173	3
21	EY3860	3
22	FC9880	3
23	FC9909	3
24	FK0108	3
25	FR1790	3
26	FW0547	3

Rank	Lot Name	Death count
27	GJ1857	3
28	GJ9259	3
29	GK1328	3
30	HG2273	3
31	HG2352	3
32	000020A	2
33	000024A	2
34	000218A	2
35	000237A	2
36	200042A	2
37	200044A	2
38	3006278	2
39	ET3674	2
40	EW0201	2
41	EY5423	2
42	FA4597	2
43	FA5765	2
44	FF2018	2
45	FK0595	2
46	FK6302	2
47	FM7534	2
48	ET9319	2
49	GD9572	2
50	GJ1842	2
51	GJ7141	2
52	000006A	1

Rank	Lot Name	Death count
53	000007A	1
54	000008A	1
55	000048A	1
56	000204A	1
57	000211A	1
58	000214A	1
59	000233A	1
60	000248A	1
61	000268A	1
62	200056A	1
63	3002181	1
64	3005785	1
65	3005787	1
66	3005890	1
67	3006343	1
68	400085A	1
69	400087A	1
70	400088A	1
71	400089A	1
72	400092A	1
73	400108A	1
74	400181A	1
75	400189A	1
76	400195A	1
77	710005A	1
78	710007A	1

Rank	Lot Name	Death count
79	710008A	1
80	EW0203	1
81	EY0779	1
82	EY4834	1
83	FA2453	1
84	FA5829	1
85	FC5295	1
86	FC5947	1
87	FD0348	1
88	FF2782	1
89	FF5357	1
90	FG0978	1
91	FH0151	1
92	FK7441	1
93	FK7646	1
94	FN2726	1
95	FP9647	1
96	GD9135	1
97	GD9571	1
98	GE6396	1
99	GJ7139	1
100	GJ9258	1
101	HD9868	1
102	HG2347	1
103	HH1299	1

Table S3

Figure S1

A**B**

Year	Deaths		
	Observed	Expected	Excess
2020	1,372,755	1,389,105	-16,350
2021	1,439,856	1,407,294	32,562
2022	1,569,050	1,425,483	143,567
2023	1,576,016	1,443,672	132,344
2024	1,605,378	1,461,861	143,517

Figure S2

Simple mortality rate

Interval-specific mortality rate

Figure S3

Simple mortality rate

Days from final vaccination to death

Interval-specific mortality rate

Days from final vaccination to death

Figure S4

Figure S5